

BIAXIAL STRESS FATIGUE TESTING OF THIN-WALLED GRP CYLINDERS

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A multistation hydraulic machine for fatigue testing thin-walled GRP cylinders under combined internal pressure and axial load has been developed. The machine is described and results are given for chopped strand mat/polyester resin cylinders. Inevitable joints in the reinforcement had a negligible effect on the static strength of the cylinders, but were found to be responsible for a much reduced fatigue strength compared with that of flat specimens. Batch differences in the materials also had a considerable effect especially under biaxial tension. It was difficult to confirm the applicability of any particular failure theory under biaxial stress fatigue. In the tension-tension quadrant however the results tended to fall well inside the maximum principal stress boundary.

Introduction

Safe-life design in fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) requires the development of analytical or empirical rules to allow for a wide variety of loading and environmental conditions. In most applications materials are subjected to multiaxial stress conditions. Many theories have been proposed for predicting the strength of FRP under complex stress conditions. These are necessarily more complicated than yield theories for isotropic materials because the material strengths change with the direction and mode of loading. The variety of possible failure modes and design failure criteria (i.e. states of damage) adds to the complexity of the situation. Table I lists some of the functions (specialised for plane stress) which have been applied as potential failure theories for FRP. The Group 1 theories only require simple strength data based on uniaxial tests parallel to the material axes or in-plane shear loading. The Group 2 theories require the results of a complex stress test to evaluate a constant or the interaction coefficient of the strength tensor. All the theories except the strength tensor theories (8,9) require the local stresses to be transformed to the principal material axes.

Designers are concerned to know which of the proposed theories adequately represents the observed behaviour of materials and the scale of effort required to evaluate the necessary design data associated with each theory. In the general stress state there are six components of stress and this makes pictorial representation of failure theories impossible. However, in the special case of plane stress there are only three non-zero stress components ($\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_6$ referred to the principal material axes or $\sigma'_x, \sigma'_y, \tau'_{xy}$, referred to the general element) and these can be represented in Cartesian space to form a failure surface (10). It is generally accepted that a failure surface should be closed and that the origin of the stress space should lie within the surface. The functions in Table I define either sets of planes or ellipsoidal surfaces. The Group 2 theories in Table I can form open-ended surfaces unless the constant or interaction term lies within certain values. Tsai and Wu (9) included a stability criterion to ensure that the surface is closed. In reality none of the theories can be represented by a single unique surface because the principal strengths of any material are subject to scatter. However a single surface would be expected for the mean values or for arbitrarily defined working stresses. For the Group 1 theories the strengths define points on the principal axes of the failure surface and complex stress results are only required to test the representation elsewhere. For the Group 2 theories any complex stress test result should define the complete surface. However it has been shown (10, 11, 12, 13) that the shape of the surface can be extremely sensitive to small changes in the value of the complex strengths and that there are optimal stress ratios for the determination of the interaction coefficients.

Numerous methods have been proposed for biaxial stress testing

of isotropic materials. However for FRP only the off-axis tensile or compression test, the thin-walled cylinder test and, the cruciform specimen test appear to be useful. There are problems with all of these. The off-axis test is attractive because it is relatively cheap to perform and requires only a standard testing machine for either static or fatigue testing (14). However it only permits exploration of a limited part of the failure surface; the stress ratios are not favourable for the determination of the interaction coefficients; the specimen has to be long enough for rotational constraints at the grips not to affect the centre section; and there are significant width effects. The thin-walled cylinder test and the cruciform test require expensive specimens and special purpose testing machines. However with the cylinder test using various combinations of axial load, internal pressure, and torsion extensive coverage of the failure surface is possible. Wu (11) has reported using a computer controlled machine for combined axial load and torsion testing and the machine can apparently be used for both static and fatigue testing. Owen and Found (15) have reported the use of a somewhat less sophisticated multistation hydraulic machine which subjects cylinders to combined axial load and internal pressure. Their machine has now been used for an extensive programme of static and fatigue testing of polyester resins reinforced with both glass chopped strand mat and a plain weave glass fabric. The results are far too numerous to present as a single paper. The present paper is devoted to the chopped strand mat results and to some of the problems encountered in testing. Whilst chopped strand mat/polyester resin laminates are macroscopically plane isotropic they have different tensile and compressive strengths and the failure processes are controlled by microscopic anisotropy. Their failure under complex stress conditions is more adequately represented by some of the failure theories in Table I than by isotropic theories (15). However since chopped strand mat/polyester resin laminates are macroscopically plane isotropic the results can be presented in terms of principal stresses when the failure surface becomes a curve on the principal stress plane ($\sigma_6=0$). Detailed accounts of the work have been presented in theses by Found (16) and Griffiths (13).

Owen and Found (15) reported static and fatigue tests on chopped strand mat/polyester resin cylinders and observed three states of damage, transverse fibre debonding, resin cracking, and rupture at five nominal principal stress ratios $R = -1.0, -0.5, 0, +0.5,$ and $+1.0$. They found that the fatigue effect was severe in the tension-tension quadrant especially at $R = +1.0$; under both static and fatigue loading all the biaxial stress results fell well inside the principal stress theory of failure; it was necessary to use a complex stress result with one of the Group 2 theories (Table I) to obtain a good representation of the data; and there were several anomalies in the results. The most important anomaly was concerned with the $R = 0$ case. At this condition the axial stress in the cylinder is just zero and the cylinder results should correspond with flat laminate results for uniaxial stress. Under static loading

this agreement was obtained, but under fatigue loading the S-N curve for the cylinders was much lower than for flat laminates. Possible explanations were not evaluated.

Equipment and Method of Testing

Figure 1 is a photograph of the multistation rig for applying combined axial loading and internal pressure to thin-walled cylinders. From left to right there is a loading frame arranged for static testing using a hand operated pump, a control console with X-Y recorders, two loading frames for fatigue tests, a hydraulic pulsator pump, and two further fatigue loading frames. Figure 2 is a diagrammatic representation of one of the loading frames. Two substantial end plates A are separated by four columns B to provide a stiff frame. Within the frame in a single chain are the axial load cell C, the axial load ram D, and the specimen E with end caps F and loading bars G, H. Oil is supplied to the system via the loading ram and hence through a small diameter hole in the lower loading bar to the interior of the specimen. Air can be released through the centre of the upper loading bar, J. Since the same supply of oil (Shell "Tellus" 15, a mineral oil) is used for the ram and the cylinder the principal stresses in the cylinder are always in phase. In order to vary the principal stress ratio it is necessary to have a set of interchangeable rams of different diameters. Nine different axial loading rams are available, some acting in tension and some in compression to give principal stress ratios above or below 0.5. It will be noticed in Figure 1 that each loading frame has a different diameter ram. With the multistation machine and careful planning of the test programme no great inconvenience is occasioned by this method. In practice there is some friction at the loading ram and both the axial load and the pressure are monitored. The axial stress is calculated from the axial load and the hoop stress from the pressure. Under fatigue loading conditions the ram friction is low enough to permit rotation of the ram pistons to accommodate the torsional displacements which occur in cylinders with off-axis reinforcements. For static tests the oil is supplied by a hand-operated pump and for fatigue tests by a pulsator pump. The latter has been fully described by Owen (17). The pulsator has five cylinders with pistons driven by a common eccentric. The cylinders are hydraulically independent so that they can be adjusted separately and there is one cylinder for each loading frame. By moving a cylinder in or out relative to the eccentric the piston closes the inlet ports earlier or later in the stroke. Once the ports are closed a predetermined amount of oil is forced into a closed elastic system consisting of the specimen, the ram, and the associated pipework. The maximum working pressure is 13.8 MN/m^2 (2000 lbf/in^2). Almost all of the elastic work is recovered in each cycle and so power consumption and heating effects in the oil are very small. The machine is virtually silent apart from the electric motor driving the pulsator pump. Small amounts of leakage are automatically made up each time the inlet ports are uncovered

by means of a low pressure supply. The pump has a variable speed drive covering the range 55-330 cycles/min and is normally used at 100 cycles/min. The hydraulic circuit for each frame includes a solenoid operated dumping valve and a pressure operated switch. If the switch remains closed for ten seconds continuously the specimen is assumed to have failed. A simple electronic circuit operates the dumping valve and also interrupts a cycle counter. The pulsator continues to run and to provide pulsating pressure for any other specimens still on test. A comprehensive description of the design of the machine has been given by Found (16).

A considerable amount of supplementary fatigue testing was carried out on flat laminate specimens subjected to axial loading. These tests were conducted in the axial loading fatigue machine previously described by Owen (17). Five loading frames are available and can apply any combination of mean and alternating load within the extreme limits of ± 26.7 kN (± 6000 lbf). They are also driven by a pulsator pump. As far as is possible for FRP (18) the test methods were in accordance with B.S.3518, "Methods of Fatigue Testing".

Materials and Specimen Preparation

Details of the materials used are summarised in Table II. It is more difficult to obtain consistent properties with chopped strand mat/polyester resin laminates than with other types of GRP. Since 1963 a considerable volume of work has been carried out at the University of Nottingham on this material, and the main causes of variability have been established as follows :

- a) within the laminate; (i) directionality and superficial density variation in the nominally isotropic and uniform mat; (ii) thickness (and hence glass content) variation across the laminate; (iii) stretching of the reinforcement during the rolling and wetting-out process.
- b) between laminates; (i) thickness variation; (ii) batch variability both of mat and resin; (iii) curing cycle

Coefficients of variation of 5% on glass content and ultimate tensile strength can be obtained within a large flat laminate (533 x 685 x 6.4 mm³) and slightly more over several boards by using a single batch of resin and reinforcement, cutting reinforcement layers alternately along and across the roll, visual inspection of the reinforcement for unusually thick or thin regions, and preparing laminates within a steel picture-frame mould to control stretch and thickness. Some compromise is needed over void content since it is possible neither to pre-wet the mat nor to press out surplus resin as is the practice with fabric reinforced laminates. Weighed amounts of resin are subdivided into the same number of parts as the number of layers of reinforcement in the laminate. With a single layer an almost void-free laminate can be obtained but as the laminate thickness increases it becomes more difficult to remove all air especially at strand cross-overs. Wetting-out and void removal are improved by slow

gelling and cold-curing provided that sufficient catalyst is used to obtain a full cure by post-curing. This technique also tends to give better laminate properties than more rapid cures. In short, some voids must be tolerated but the void content of laboratory laminates is low in comparison with commercial chopped strand mat/polyester resin mouldings.

The procedure for making thin-walled cylinders was as follows. A 65 mm diameter mandrel was wrapped with a single layer of "Melinex" release film. Sections of chopped strand mat 405 x 225 mm², were cut from the roll, some being cut lengthways and some crossways from the roll to avoid directional effects. The long edge of the mat was wetted with resin and allowed to adhere to the release film on the mandrel so that the long edge was parallel to the axis. As the mandrel slowly turned the rest of the mat was wetted with resin and attached to the release film until the second long edge just butted against the original edge. Additional layers of mat were added by the same procedure taking care to stagger the butt joints. By careful rolling against the slowly turning mandrel it was possible to ensure complete wetting of the mat without disturbing its position on the roller. When the lay-up was completed the outer surface was covered with a sheet of "Melinex" and the mandrel left slowly turning in contact with a light roller until the resin gelled. The cylinder so prepared was long enough to form two specimens of overall length 180 mm. For compressive axial loading conditions three layers of mat were used giving a wall thickness of 3.3mm. The ends were thickened by overwrapping with resin and glass fabric leaving a 100 mm long working section (Figure 3). For tensile axial loading two layers of mat were used giving a wall thickness of 2.3 mm and the specimens were cast into threaded end caps with epoxy resin leaving a 120 mm long working section (Figure 4). The tensile end caps were sprayed with release agent so that the specimens could be unscrewed after testing. The ends of the specimens were turned in a lathe before assembly with the end caps. Both types of end cap have a close fitting central spigot which provides axial alignment and also houses an O-ring seal. The chopped strand mat cylinders are more difficult to make than equivalent flat laminates and the void content, by visual estimate, is higher. There are resin rich layers on both inner and outer surfaces which contain the majority of the voids. Silicone rubber liners were used in the cylinders to prevent oil under pressure from being forced into the material after the advent of damage and to eliminate seepage from specimens tested to rupture. Originally for static work a cold curing rubber (Silastomer B9161, Catalyst N9162) was applied over primer MS2650 supplied by Midlands Silicones Ltd. This system is white and prevents the observation of damage. Found (16) used separate specimens without liners to observe the onset of debonding and resin cracking which were readily visible against the relatively dark mineral oil background. However the Midland Silicones system tended to peel under repeated loading and another system was used for fatigue tests. The cylinders were cleaned with acetone and treated with ICI Primer OP which was

allowed to dry for half an hour. The cylinder was then coated with ICI Silcoset 105 cold-curing silicone rubber with added carbon black to make damage visible. The carbon black tended to make the liner porous and a second layer of unfilled rubber was added.

Flat laminates were hand-laid on "Melinex" film supported on glass plates. Two and three-layer laminates were prepared to simulate as closely as possible the material forming the cylinders. Some of the laminates incorporated butt joints at known positions. The flat laminates were cut into the specimen shapes shown in Figure 5. The specimen blanks were cut using electro-bonded diamond slitting wheels and the profiles were cut using a pantograph-type copying machine with electro-bonded diamond routing cutters.

Results

(a) Effect of glass content on the strength of flat laminates

Figures 6 and 7 show the effect of glass content variation on the ultimate compressive and ultimate tensile strength of flat laminates, and also show the clear difference between batches of material obtained by Found and by Griffiths at an interval of approximately 2 years. In general where cylinders and flat laminates were intended to be the same, the cylinders had a slightly lower glass content averaging 32% compared with approximately 34% for flat laminates. This has a significant effect on the tensile strength and has to be allowed for wherever cylinder and flat laminate results are compared. It can easily be shown that the glass content is inversely proportional to thickness for laminates containing the same number of layers of mat and that there is a strong correlation between modulus and glass content. In subsequent work it has been assumed that similar relationships between glass content and strength would apply to cylinders tested at various R values. However the determination of such relationships for each R value would be hopelessly uneconomic.

(b) Static tests of cylinders

Figure 8 shows static strength data, obtained originally by Found (16), at five values of R (nominally -1.0, -0.5, 0, +0.5, and +1.0) and with the onset of transverse fibre debonding and resin cracking observed as well as rupture. The results do not correspond exactly with the nominal R values because of ram friction. The results for $R = +\infty$ and $R = -\infty$ are flat laminate results in tension and compression respectively, adjusted for glass content. At rupture the agreement between $R = \infty$ (axial stress only) and $R = 0$ (hoop stress only) values is good. The curves in Figure 8 are estimates and do not correspond with any particular theory of failure. However Owen and Found (15) showed that only the Group 2 failure theories (Table I) could provide a good fit with the data obtained for all three criteria of failure.

Figure 9 shows additional rupture data obtained by Griffiths' (13) for biaxial stress ratios $R = -0.75, -0.25, 0, +0.25, +0.75,$ and $+1.0$ together with Founds' rupture data. The two sets of data appear to be generally compatible but if the means of the Found and Griffiths data are plotted separately (Figure 10) and the failure theories tested against the data it is seen that the Griffiths results indicate a smaller effect for the non-zero second principal stress. This is taken to be another manifestation of material batch effects. In Figure 10 it should be noted that the results plotted between $R = +1.0$ and $R = +\infty$ are reflections about $R = +1.0$ of the results between $R = 0$ and $R = +1.0$. This is considered justifiable since the material is macroscopically plane isotropic and the $R = 0$ and $R = +\infty$ results are the same. The curves in Figure 10 represent the failure theories. The principal strengths shown in the figure were used to evaluate the curves, and the additional constants for the Group 2 theories were evaluated from the mean of all the results at $R = +1.0$. The best fit is given by the Group 2 theories.

(c) Biaxial stress fatigue results

Found (16) obtained a number of S-N curves from tests on thin walled cylinders at several values of R and for three different states of damage. These were presented as constant life diagrams by Owen and Found (15). The diagrams for rupture and resin cracking are reproduced as Figures 11 and 12. The curves in the figures are sketched to represent the results and do not conform to any particular theory of failure. The fatigue curves were not extended to the $R = +\infty$ and $R = -\infty$ axes because of the anomaly explained below. The anomaly and the severe effect of repeated loading at the $R = 1$ condition are the main features of the results.

(d) The effect of reinforcement joints

Figure 13 shows a comparison of the S-N curves obtained by Found (16) and by Griffiths (13) for flat specimens under repeated tension and for cylinders at $R = 0$. Griffiths' results show an even greater discrepancy than Found's between the two types of data. Several possible explanations were considered: size effect (the axial length of the cylinders is far greater than the neck width of the flat specimens); the effect of oil on the failure process (although the cylinders have silicone rubber liners some leakage occurs at the ends and wets the outer surface); the effect of radial stress at the inside surface (third principal stress); and possible differences in glass content. The axial load fatigue results were consistent with results obtained from other projects at the time and previous work (19) had shown that the effect of glass content tends to diminish at longer lives. Initially overlooked was the possibility that joints in the reinforcement may behave differently under static and fatigue loading.

A number of two-layer and three-layer flat laminates were pre-

pared, some with butt joints in one surface layer to simulate the joint in the inner layer of a cylinder. Specimens were cut so that the joints were either parallel or perpendicular to the specimen axis at the neck (Figure 5). These specimens were subjected both to static and fatigue loading in tension both in air and immersed in Shell "Tellus" 15 oil. The results are shown as S-N curves in Figure 14 (the effect of joints) and Figure 15 (the effect of oil). In Figure 16 individual fatigue results are plotted for transverse butt jointed specimens tested in air and oil and for cylinders ($R = 0$) prepared from the same batches of material. A detailed analysis of the corresponding static results, making due allowance for glass content variation showed that the effects of both oil immersion and joints were negligible. The conclusion is inescapable that it is the reinforcement joints which dominate the fatigue behaviour and give rise to the previously reported anomaly.

Unless a joint is identified in some way at the laminating stage it is remarkably difficult to locate subsequently and hence demonstrate the relationship between joints and failure. If transverse sections are cut and polished by the usual metallographic techniques, thus showing fields of resin containing cut fibres, it is quite impossible to identify the joints. It has been found that they can be revealed by the following procedure: surface grind down to the plane of interest (by internal grinding in the case of cylinders); treat the ground surface in hydrofluoric acid to etch out the glass from the resin; fill the resultant surface with indian ink, dry, and wipe clean to leave the glass filaments replaced by ink. Figures 17(a) and 17(b) show two samples prepared in this way after static loading until a resin crack first appeared at the joint. They are also present elsewhere and are indicated by the light zones out of focus below the surface. Resin cracks reflect light and are readily observed when the specimen is manipulated in front of a lamp. The characteristic feature of the joint is the lack of strands crossing the joint region. Figure 18 shows an axial load fatigue specimen with a crack at a joint across the neck. Fatigue specimens of this shape are usually intensively resin cracked over the middle third of their length and the feature here is the relative absence of such damage away from the joint region. Figure 19 shows the appearance of the prepared inner surface of a cylinder revealing a joint and showing the association of a fatigue failure with the joint after testing at $R = 0$.

(e) Further biaxial stress fatigue results

Figure 20 represents all the fatigue results obtained for the rupture of cylinders by both Found ($R = -1.0, -0.5, 0, +0.5$ and $+1.0$) and Griffiths ($R = -0.75, -0.25, 0, +0.25$ and $+0.75$). These graphs include the results of over 80 individual fatigue tests on cylinders. Together with the static tests and damage studies over 130 cylinders have been tested. To allow for the discrepancies between Found's and Griffiths' data revealed at $R = 0$ (Figure 13) all

Griffiths' S-N curves have been scaled by a factor determined from the $R = 0$ curves to allow for both batch and glass content differences. The data for R values between -1.0 and 0 are consistent. However a further large discrepancy exists between Found's data for $R = +0.5$ and $R = +1.0$ and Griffiths' data for $R = +0.75$. This is shown most clearly in Figure 21 where the 10^6 cycle fatigue strengths are plotted in the σ_x, σ_y plane. In the tension-tension quadrant Found's data indicate a serious biaxial effect whereas for Griffiths' data the effect of the second stress is small. Also shown in Figure 21 are the failure theories of Table I. The fatigue strength in axial compression ($R = -\infty$) is taken from previously published work by Owen and Found (15). The Group 1 theories depend only on the uniaxial strengths and the failure envelopes are determined without difficulty although they provide a poor fit to the results. The Group 2 theories give wide variations of fit. If Found's $R = +1.0$ data are used the Tsai and Wu stability criterion is violated (curve F1). If the $R = -1.0$ data is used then a very poor fit is obtained in the tensile quadrant (curve F2). If Griffiths' $R = +0.75$ data are used a better approximation is obtained (curve F3). The best fit is obtained by using the modified Marin theory and determining K_2 separately for each quadrant. Figures 22 and 23 show resin cracking damage for $R = 0$ and $R = 1$ under fatigue loading. Damage is similar to the $R = 0$ case as R changes from -1.0 to $+0.5$ i.e. unidirectional and perpendicular to the hoop stress (parallel to the joints). At higher R values it becomes multidirectional. Owen and Howe (20) observed that the intense resin cracking which occurred under fatigue loading in chopped strand mat is principally responsible for the fall in static residual strength which leads to ultimate separation. Intuitively it might be expected that the multidirectional cracking should be more severe in its effect than the unidirectional cracking. Thus the Griffiths result at $R = +0.75$ is surprising.

Discussion and Conclusions

The multistation fatigue testing machine was commissioned towards the end of 1970 and has since been used successfully to evaluate the biaxial stress fatigue properties of chopped strand mat and fabric reinforced polyester resins. The results obtained for fabric reinforcements are being offered for publication elsewhere. The machine has worked reliably and was much cheaper to build than an equivalent servo-hydraulic machine and is less demanding in terms of laboratory services (electrical power and cooling water). The direct cost of manufacture in 1970 was £8,500. If fully costed, including overheads, this figure would probably be close to £17,000. The complete investigation on chopped strand mat reinforced cylinders, together with the investigation of joint effects, took 2 years to complete. This scale of effort is unlikely to be justified in relation to most commercial applications of the materials.

The experimental difficulties arising from joints would have

occurred with any form of thin-walled cylinder testing machine. It is known that the free edge would have produced the same effect if helical wrapping had been adopted. Possibly careful teasing of the reinforcement at the joint would ameliorate the problem but this has not been demonstrated. Joint effects could be avoided by using flat specimens in a cruciform testing machine. However it would not be surprising if other problems arose in their place.

Chopped strand mat/polyester resin laminates are notoriously difficult to experiment with owing to the large scatter experienced in the results. In spite of the scatter there were marked differences between the two batches of material prepared by Found and Griffiths. In axial tension and compression (Figures 6 and 7) the Griffiths material was distinctly inferior whereas in the biaxial experiments the Griffiths cylinders were superior at $R = +0.75$ and $R = +1.0$ (Figure 10). This effect was even more pronounced in the fatigue results at 10^6 cycles. Further micro-examination of the failed cylinders might reveal differences in the resin cracking behaviour which would account for this. All the specimens have been preserved in the hope that man-power will be available for this to be done. It is also known that the two batches of reinforcement were manufactured on different plants and it is possible that differences in the reinforcement have occurred which could have produced the improved biaxial stress properties.

The effect of reinforcement joints on the fatigue properties of the cylinders is a nuisance from the point of view of experimental evaluation of failure theories but nevertheless it may be of great significance industrially. Chopped strand mat is conventionally supplied in rolls approximately 1 m wide and in various superficial densities. Large structures inevitably contain butt or lap-joints in the reinforcement. It seems highly probable that these are a source of weakness under repeated or time-dependent loading. Furthermore once a macro-crack has been initiated the fracture toughness of the material is low and propagation will continue at relatively low nominal stresses. Owen and Bishop (21) have shown the relevance of conventional crack propagation laws for this type of material.

The results obtained under fatigue condition demonstrate how difficult it is to confirm the relevance of failure theories. In the absence of joints the fatigue strength for the $R = 0$ and $R = +\infty$ (pure hoop and pure axial stress) cases should both be equivalent to the fatigue strength of flat specimens of equivalent material. Both of these strengths will be reduced by joint effects but to different extents as indicated by Figure 14. However in Figure 21 the $R = +\infty$ strength was taken as equal to the strength in the $R = 0$ case since no axial loading results were available for cylinders. A further complication is caused by the fact that there is no means to evaluate the interactive effect of a joint when both principal stresses are non-zero. As previously noted by Owen and Found (15) the best fit to the results is provided by the Group 2 theories of

Table I. This is because of the presence of a constant or an interaction coefficient which can be used to fit the data to a biaxial stress condition. This can be done fairly accurately for the Found or Griffiths data separately. It is clear however that big differences are produced in the failure envelope by fitting the curve to different sets of experimental data. In practice it is probably the tension-tension quadrant which is the most important since in large structures buckling will control failure if compressive stresses are present. In the tension-tension quadrant it is important to note the data fell well inside the principal stress criterion of failure in most cases. It is likely that for design purposes a circular arc (that is the Norris Interaction Theory (7)) is a reasonably safe prediction in most cases, but this should always be confirmed by experiment.

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FAILURE CRITERION

KEY TO
FIGS

REFERENCE

	A	$\sigma_1 = F_1; \quad \sigma_2 = F_2; \quad \sigma_6 = F_6$	
	B	$\left[\frac{\sigma_1}{F_1} \right]^2 - \frac{1}{F_2^2} + \frac{1}{F_3^2} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 + \left[\frac{\sigma_2}{F_2} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{\sigma_6}{F_6} \right]^2 = 1$	
	B	$\left[\frac{\sigma_1}{F_1} \right]^2 - \frac{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}{F_1^2} + \left[\frac{\sigma_2}{F_2} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{\sigma_6}{F_6} \right]^2 = 1$	
	C	$\left[\frac{\sigma_1}{F_1} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{\sigma_2}{F_2} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{\sigma_6}{F_6} \right]^2 = 1$	
	D	$\left[\frac{\sigma_1}{F_1} \right]^2 - \frac{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}{F_1 F_2} + \left[\frac{\sigma_2}{F_2} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{\sigma_6}{F_6} \right]^2 = 1; \quad \left[\frac{\sigma_1}{F_1} \right]^2 = 1; \quad \left[\frac{\sigma_2}{F_2} \right]^2 = 1$	
	E	$\frac{\sigma_1^2 - \sigma_1 \sigma_2}{F_1 C F_1 t} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{F_2 C F_2 t} + \left[\frac{F_1 C - F_1 t}{F_1 C F_1 t} \right] \sigma_1 + \left[\frac{F_2 C - F_2 t}{F_2 C F_2 t} \right] \sigma_2 + \left[\frac{\sigma_6}{F_6} \right]^2 = 1$	
	F	$\frac{\sigma_1^2 - K_2 \sigma_1 \sigma_2}{F_1 C F_1 t} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{F_2 C F_2 t} + \left[\frac{F_1 C - F_1 t}{F_1 C F_1 t} \right] \sigma_1 + \left[\frac{F_2 C - F_2 t}{F_2 C F_2 t} \right] \sigma_2 + \left[\frac{\sigma_6}{F_6} \right]^2 = 1$	
	F	$\frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1}{F_1 t} - \frac{1}{F_1 C} \right] \sigma_1 + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1}{F_2 t} - \frac{1}{F_2 C} \right] \sigma_2 + \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{1}{F_1 t} + \frac{1}{F_1 C} \right]^2 \sigma_1^2 + \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{1}{F_2 t} + \frac{1}{F_2 C} \right]^2 \sigma_2^2 + 2H_{12} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 + \left[\frac{\sigma_6}{F_6} \right]^2 = 1$	
GROUP 1			
	F	$\left[\frac{1}{F_1 t} - \frac{1}{F_1 C} \right] \sigma_1 + \left[\frac{1}{F_2 t} - \frac{1}{F_2 C} \right] \sigma_2 + \frac{\sigma_1^2}{F_1 t F_1 C} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{F_2 t F_2 C} + 2H_{12} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 + \left[\frac{\sigma_6}{F_6} \right]^2 = 1$	
		<p style="text-align: center;">and $\frac{1}{F_1 t F_1 C} \cdot \frac{1}{F_2 t F_2 C} - H_{12} \gg 0$ for stability</p>	
GROUP 2			
	F	$\left[\frac{1}{F_1 t} - \frac{1}{F_1 C} \right] \sigma_1 + \left[\frac{1}{F_2 t} - \frac{1}{F_2 C} \right] \sigma_2 + \frac{\sigma_1^2}{F_1 t F_1 C} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{F_2 t F_2 C} + 2H_{12} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 + \left[\frac{\sigma_6}{F_6} \right]^2 = 1$	

TABLE I Failure theories which have been suggested for anisotropic materials

Chopped Strand Mat	"SuprEmat" (600 g/m ²)	Fibreglass Ltd.
Polyester resin -	Beetle L2615	BIP Chemicals Ltd.
	Maleic Anhydride	1 mol
	Phthalic Anhydride	1 mol
	Propylene Glycol	3 mol
	Alkyd/Styrene Ratio	65/35
	Hydroquinone	0.008% on blended resin
Catalyst	MEKP	1%
Accelerator	Cobalt naphthenate	½%
Room temperature cure		18 h
Postcure		3 h at 80°C.

TABLE II Materials

Nomenclature

σ_x, σ_y	Nominal principal stresses in the hoop and axial directions
$\sigma'_x, \sigma'_y, \sigma'_{xy}$	Normal and in-plane shear stresses on a general element of material.
$\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_6$	Normal and shear stresses in the directions of the principal material axes of FRP. To apply a failure theory to a chopped strand mat reinforced material put $\sigma_1 = \sigma_x$, $\sigma_2 = \sigma_y$, and $\sigma_6 = 0$.
F_1, F_2, F_6	Strengths corresponding to σ_1, σ_2 , and σ_6 .
F_{1t}, F_{2t}	Tensile strengths in the principal material directions.
F_{1c}, F_{2c}	Compressive strengths in the principal material directions.
K_2	A constant evaluated from a combined stress test.
H_{12}	Interaction component of a strength tensor.
S-N curve	Conventional stress-log life fatigue curve.
R	Principal stress ratio, σ_y/σ_x .

1. Biaxial stress fatigue machine

2. Section through a loading frame:

A, end plates; B, columns; C, axial load cell; D, axial load ram; E, specimen; F, end caps; G, upper loading bar; H, lower loading bar; J, bleed valve; K, centering bush; L, safety screen.

3. Axial compression cylinder with end cap.

4. Axial tension cylinder with end cap.

5. Flat laminate specimens: a, compression, static and fatigue; b, static tension, c, tensile fatigue. All dimensions in mm.

6. Relationship between glass content and ultimate compressive strength

Found (16): 18 results; correlation coefficient, +0.27;
Standard error of estimate, ± 10.63 MN/m².

Griffiths (13): 33 results; correlation coefficient, +0.32;
Standard error of estimate, ± 10.06 MN/m².

7. Relationship between glass content and ultimate tensile strength

Found (16): 30 results; correlation coefficient, +0.80;
Standard error of estimate, ± 4.24 MN/m².

Griffiths (13): 43 results; correlation coefficient, +0.80;
Standard error of estimate, ± 6.54 MN/m².

8. Static strength results for three states of damage (15).

9. Static strength results for rupture (13).

10. Failure theories from Table I fitted to strength results (for key to letters see Table I).

11. Fatigue results for rupture of cylinders as constant life curves (15).

12. Fatigue results for resin cracking of cylinders as constant life curves (15).

13. Zero-tension stress fatigue results for flat specimens compared with fatigue results for cylinders at R=0.

14. Effect of oil on the zero-tension fatigue properties of flat laminate specimens.

15. Effect of joints on the zero-tension fatigue properties of flat laminate specimens.

16. Comparison of fatigue data for flat specimens with joints in the reinforcement with cylinder results (R=0)

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17a Static loading, resin cracking at a joint in a flat specimen 17b Static loading resin cracking near a joint in a flat specimen.

18. Axial load fatigue failure at a joint in a flat specimen.

19. Fatigue failure at a cylinder joint, $R=0$.

20. Comparison fatigue curves for cylinders at various values of R .

21. Failure theories of Table I fitted to fatigue results at 10^6 cycles.

22. Resin cracking in fatigue, $R=0$.

23. Resin cracking in fatigue, $R=1$.